

Credit Valuation Adjustment Framework

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a for calculating credit value adjustment (CVA) and wrong way risk. The framework relies on the probability distribution of a default time/jump. Based on our theory, we propose a novel cash-flow-based framework for calculating bilateral CVA at the counterparty portfolio level. This framework can easily incorporate various credit mitigation techniques, such as netting agreements and margin agreements, and can capture wrong way risk. Numerical results show that these credit mitigation techniques and wrong way risk have significant impacts on CVA.

Key Words: credit value adjustment (CVA), wrong way risk, credit risk, collateral

As a consequence, the International Accounting Standard (IAS) 39 requires banks to provide a fair-value adjustment due to counterparty risk. Although credit value adjustment (CVA) became mandatory in 2000, it received a little attention until the recent financial crises in which the profit and loss (P&L) swings due to CVA changes were measured in billions of dollars. Interest in CVA began to grow. Now CVA has become the first line of defense and the central part of counterparty risk management.

The earlier works on CVA are mainly focused on unilateral CVA that assumes that only one counterparty is defaultable and the other one is default-free. The unilateral treatment neglects the fact that both counterparties may default, i.e., counterparty risk can be bilateral. A trend that has become increasingly relevant and popular has been to consider the bilateral nature of counterparty credit risk. Although most institutions view bilateral considerations as important in order to agree on new transactions, Hull and White (2013) argue that bilateral CVA is more controversial than unilateral CVA as the possibility that a dealer might default is in theory a benefit to the dealer.

In general, risky valuation can be classified into two categories: the *default time approach* (DTA) and the *default probability approach* (DPA). The DTA involves the default time explicitly. Most CVA models in the literature (Brigo and Capponi (2008), Lipton and Sepp (2009), Pykhtin and Zhu (2006) and Gregory (2009), etc.) are based on this approach.

The current popular CVA methodology (Pykhtin and Zhu (2006) and Gregory (2009), etc.) is first derived using DTA and then discretized over a time grid in order to yield a feasible solution. The discretization, however, is inaccurate. In fact, this model has never been rigorously proved. Since CVA is used for financial accounting and pricing, its accuracy is essential. Moreover, this current model is based on a well-known assumption, in which credit exposure and counterparty's credit quality are independent. Obviously, it can not capture wrong/right way risk properly.

An intuitive way of understanding these backward recursive behaviours is that we can think of that any contingent claim embeds two default options. In other words, when entering an OTC

derivatives transaction, one party grants the other party an option to default and, at the same time, also receives an option to default itself. In theory, default may occur at any time. Therefore, the default options are American style options that normally require a backward induction valuation.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses unilateral risky valuation and unilateral CVA. Section 2 elaborates bilateral risky valuation and bilateral CVA. Section 3 presents numerical results. The conclusions are given in Section 4. . All proofs and a practical framework that embraces netting agreements, margining agreements and wrong/right way risk are contained in the appendices.

1. Unilateral Risky Valuation and Unilateral CVA

The default model is based on the reduced-form approach proposed by Duffie and Singleton (1999) and Jarrow and Turnbull (1994), which does not explain the event of default endogenously, but characterizes it exogenously by a jump process. The stopping (or default) time τ of a firm is modeled as a Cox arrival process (also known as a doubly stochastic Poisson process) whose first jump occurs at default and is defined as,

$$\tau = \inf \left\{ t : \int_0^t h(s, \Phi_s) ds \geq \Delta \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $h(t)$ or $h(t, \Phi_t)$ denotes the stochastic hazard rate or arrival intensity dependent on an exogenous common state Γ_t , and Δ is a unit exponential random variable independent of Φ_t .

It is well-known that the survival probability from time t to s in this framework is defined by

$$p(t, s) := P(\tau > s \mid \tau > t, Z) = \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (2a)$$

The default probability for the period (t, s) in this framework is defined by

$$q(t, s) := P(\tau \leq s \mid \tau > t, Z) = 1 - p(t, s) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (2b)$$

Two counterparties are denoted as A and B . Let valuation date be t . Consider a financial contract that promises to pay a $X_T > 0$ from party B to party A at maturity date T , and nothing before date T . All calculations in the paper are from the perspective of party A . The risk free value of the financial contract is given by

$$V^F(t) = E[D(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (3a)$$

where

$$D(t, T) = \exp\left[-\int_t^T r(u)du\right] \quad (3b)$$

where $E\{\bullet | \mathcal{F}_t\}$ denotes the expectation conditional on the \mathcal{F}_t , $D(t, T)$ denotes the risk-free discount factor at time t for the maturity T and $r(u)$ denotes the risk-free short rate at time u ($t \leq u \leq T$).

The DTA involves the default time explicitly. If there has been no default before time T (i.e., $\tau > T$), the value of the contract at T is the payoff X_T . If a default happens before T (i.e., $t < \tau \leq T$), a recovery payoff is made at the default time τ as a fraction of the market value¹ given by $\phi V(\tau)$ where ϕ is the default recovery rate and $V(\tau)$ is the market value at default. Under a risk-neutral measure, the value of this defaultable contract is the discounted expectation of all the payoffs and is given by

$$V(t) = E\left[(D(t, T) X_T 1_{\tau > T} + D(t, \tau) \phi V(\tau) 1_{\tau \leq T}) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (4)$$

where 1_Y is an indicator function that is equal to one if Y is true and zero otherwise.

Although the DTA is very intuitive, it has the disadvantage that it explicitly involves the default time/jump. We are very unlikely to have complete information about a firm's default point,

¹ Here we use the recovery of market value (RMV) assumption.

which is often inaccessible. Usually, valuation under the DTA is performed via Monte Carlo simulation.

The DPA relies on the probability distribution of the default time rather than the default time itself. We divide the time period (t, T) into n very small time intervals (Δt) and assume that a default may occur only at the end of each very small period. In our derivation, we use the approximation $\exp(y) \approx 1 + y$ for very small y . The survival and the default probabilities for the period $(t, t + \Delta t)$ are given by

$$\hat{p}(t) := p(t, t + \Delta t) = \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx 1 - h(t)\Delta t \quad (5a)$$

$$\hat{q}(t) := q(t, t + \Delta t) = 1 - \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx h(t)\Delta t \quad (5b)$$

The survival payoff is equal to the market value $V(t + \Delta t)$ and the default payoff is a fraction of the market value: $\varphi(t + \Delta t)V(t + \Delta t)$. Under a risk-neutral measure, the value of the asset at t is the expectation of all the payoffs discounted at the risk-free rate and is given by

$$V(t) = E\left\{\exp(-r(t)\Delta t) [\hat{p}(t) + \varphi(t)\hat{q}(t)]V(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \approx E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)V(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (6)$$

where $y(t) = r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi(t)) = r(t) + c(t)$ denotes the risky rate and $c(t) = h(t)(1 - \varphi(t))$ is called the (short) credit spread.

Similarly, we have

$$V(t + \Delta t) = E\left\{\exp(-y(t + \Delta t)\Delta t)V(t + 2\Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right\} \quad (7)$$

Note that $\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)$ is $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable. By definition, an $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable random variable is a random variable whose value is known at time $t + \Delta t$. Based on the *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)V(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)E\left[\exp(-y(t + \Delta t)\Delta t)V(t + 2\Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right] \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E\left\{\exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^1 y(t + i\Delta t)\Delta t\right)V(t + 2\Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

By recursively deriving from t forward over T and taking the limit as Δt approaches zero, the risky value of the asset can be expressed as

$$V(t) = E \left\{ \exp \left[- \int_t^T y(u) du \right] V(T) \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right\} \quad (9)$$

In theory, a default may happen at any time, i.e., a risky contract is continuously defaultable. This Continuous Time Risky Valuation Model is accurate but sometimes complex and expensive. For simplicity, people sometimes prefer the Discrete Time Risky Valuation Model that assumes that a default may only happen at some discrete times. A natural selection is to assume that a default may occur only on the payment dates. Fortunately, the level of accuracy for this discrete approximation is well inside the typical bid-ask spread for most applications (see O’Kane and Turnbull (2003)). From now on, we will focus on the discrete setting only, but many of the points we make are equally applicable to the continuous setting.

In the case of $X_T > 0$, the survival value is equal to the payoff X_T and the default payoff is a fraction of the payoff φX_T . Whereas in the case of $X_T \leq 0$, the contract value is the payoff itself, because the default risk of party B is irrelevant for unilateral risky valuation in this case. Therefore, we have

Proposition 1: *The unilateral risky value of the single-payment contract in a discrete-time setting is given by*

$$V(t) = E[F(t, T)X_T \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (10a)$$

where

$$F(t, T) = D(t, T) [1 - 1_{X_T \geq 0} q(t, T) (1 - \varphi(T))] \quad (10b)$$

Proof: See the appendix.

Proposition 1 can be easily extended from one-period to multiple-periods. Suppose that a defaultable contract has m cash flows. Let the m cash flows be represented as X_1, \dots, X_m with

payment dates T_1, \dots, T_m . Each cash flow may be positive or negative. We have the following proposition.

Proposition 2: *The unilateral risky value of the multiple-payment contract is given by*

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} F(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (11a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$F(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[1 - 1_{(X_{j+1} + V(T_{j+1})) \geq 0} q(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi(T_{j+1})) \right] \quad (11b)$$

Proof: See the appendix.

For an intuitive explanation, we can posit that a defaultable contract under the unilateral credit risk assumption has an embedded default option (see Sorensen and Bollier (1994)). In other words, one party entering a defaultable financial transaction actually grants the other party an option to default. If we assume that a default may occur at any time, the default option is an American style option. American options normally have backward recursive natures and require backward induction valuations.

The unilateral CVA, by definition, can be expressed as

$$CVA(t) = V^F(t) - V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\left(D(t, T_i) - \prod_{j=0}^{i-1} F(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (12)$$

Proposition 2 provides a general form for pricing a unilateral defaultable contract. Applying it to a particular situation in which we assume that all the payoffs are nonnegative, we derive the following corollary:

Corollary 1: *If all the payoffs are nonnegative, the risky value of the multiple-payments contract is given by*

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} \bar{F}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (13a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$\bar{F}(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[1 - q(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi(T_{j+1})) \right] \quad (13b)$$

The proof of this corollary is easily obtained according to Proposition 2 by setting $(X_{j+1} + V(T_{j+1})) \geq 0$, since the value of the contract at any time is also nonnegative.

The CVA in this case is given by

$$CVA(t) = V^F(t) - V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[D(t, T_i) \left(1 - \prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (1 - q(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \varphi(T_{j+1}))) \right) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (14)$$

The current popular CVA model (e.g., equation (17) in Pykhtin and Zhu (2007) and equation (3) in Gregory (2009)) is quite different from above either equation (12) or equation (14). As a matter of fact, the current CVA model has never been rigorously proved. In order to reflect the economic value of counterparty credit risk, to measure the profit and loss of a bank and to provide proper incentives to traders, a good CVA model must be not only rigorous and accurate but also feasible to implement.

2. Bilateral Risky Valuation and Bilateral CVA

Two counterparties are denoted as A and B . The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. Therefore, the default indicator Y_j for party j ($j=A, B$) follows a Bernoulli distribution, which takes value 1 with default probability q_j and value 0 with survival probability p_j , i.e., $P\{Y_j = 0\} = p_j$ and $P\{Y_j = 1\} = q_j$. The marginal default distributions can be determined by the reduced-form models. The joint distributions of a bivariate Bernoulli variable can be easily obtained via the marginal distributions by introducing extra correlations.

Consider a pair of random variables (Y_A, Y_B) that has a bivariate Bernoulli distribution.

The joint probability representations are given by

$$p_{00} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0) = p_A p_B + \sigma_{AB} \quad (15a)$$

$$p_{01} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1) = p_A q_B - \sigma_{AB} \quad (15b)$$

$$p_{10} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0) = q_A p_B - \sigma_{AB} \quad (15c)$$

$$p_{11} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1) = q_A q_B + \sigma_{AB} \quad (15d)$$

where $E(Y_j) = q_j$, $\sigma_j^2 = p_j q_j$, $\sigma_{AB} := E[(Y_A - q_A)(Y_B - q_B)] = \rho_{AB} \sigma_A \sigma_B = \rho_{AB} \sqrt{q_A p_A q_B p_B}$ where ρ_{AB} denotes the default correlation coefficient and σ_{AB} denotes the default covariance.

Table 1. Payoffs of a bilaterally defaultable contract

This table displays all possible payoffs at time T . In the case of $X_T > 0$, there are a total of four possible states at time T : i) Both A and B survive with probability p_{00} . The contract value is equal to the payoff X_T . ii) A defaults but B survives with probability p_{10} . The contract value is $\bar{\varphi}_B X_T$, where $\bar{\varphi}_B$ represents the non-default recovery rate². $\bar{\varphi}_B = 0$ represents the one-way settlement rule, while $\bar{\varphi}_B = 1$ represents the two-way settlement rule. iii) A survives but B defaults with probability p_{01} . The contract value is $\varphi_B X_T$, where φ_B represents the default recovery rate. iv) Both A and B default with probability p_{11} . The contract value is $\varphi_{AB} X_T$, where φ_{AB} denotes the joint recovery rate when both parties A and B default simultaneously. A similar logic applies to the case of $X_T < 0$.

State		$Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0$	$Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0$	$Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1$	$Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1$
Comments		A & B survive	A defaults, B survives	A survives, B defaults	A & B default
Probability		p_{00}	p_{10}	p_{01}	p_{11}
Payoff	$X_T > 0$	X_T	$\bar{\varphi}_B X_T$	$\varphi_B X_T$	$\varphi_{AB} X_T$
	$X_T < 0$	X_T	$\varphi_A X_T$	$\bar{\varphi}_A X_T$	$\varphi_{AB} X_T$

² There are two default settlement rules in the market. The *one-way payment rule* was specified by the early ISDA master agreement. The non-defaulting party is not obligated to compensate the defaulting party if the remaining market value of the instrument is positive for the defaulting party. The *two-way payment rule* is based on current ISDA documentation. The non-defaulting party will pay the full market value of the instrument to the defaulting party if the contract has positive value to the defaulting party.

At time T , there are a total of four ($2^2 = 4$) possible states shown in Table 1. The risky value of the contract is the discounted expectation of the payoffs and is given by the following proposition.

Proposition 3: *The bilateral risky value of the single-payment contract is given by*

$$V(t) = E[K(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] = E[D(t, T)(1_{X_T \geq 0}k_B(t, T) + 1_{X_T < 0}k_A(t, T))X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (16a)$$

where

$$k_B(t, T) = p_B(t, T)p_A(t, T) + \varphi_B(T)q_B(t, T)p_A(t, T) + \bar{\varphi}_B(T)p_B(t, T)q_A(t, T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)q_B(t, T)q_A(t, T) + \sigma_{AB}(t, T)(1 - \varphi_B(T) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)) \quad (16b)$$

$$k_A(t, T) = p_B(t, T)p_A(t, T) + \varphi_A(T)q_A(t, T)p_B(t, T) + \bar{\varphi}_A(T)p_A(t, T)q_B(t, T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)q_B(t, T)q_A(t, T) + \sigma_{AB}(t, T)(1 - \varphi_A(T) - \bar{\varphi}_A(T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)) \quad (16c)$$

Proof: See the appendix.

Using a similar derivation as in Proposition 2, we can easily extend Proposition 3 from one-period to multiple-periods. Suppose that a defaultable contract has m cash flows. Let the m cash flows be represented as X_i with payment dates T_i , where $i = 1, \dots, m$. Each cash flow may be positive or negative. The bilateral risky value of the multiple-payment contract is given by

Proposition 4: *The bilateral risky value of the multiple-payment contract is given by*

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} K(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (17a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$K(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1})\left(1_{(X_{j+1} + V(T_{j+1})) \geq 0}k_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) + 1_{(X_{j+1} + V(T_{j+1})) < 0}k_A(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) \quad (17b)$$

where $k_A(T_j, T_{j+1})$ and $k_B(T_j, T_{j+1})$ are defined in Proposition 3.

Proof: The proof is similar to Proposition 2 by replacing $F(T_j, T_{j-1})$ with $K(T_j, T_{j-1})$.

There is a common misconception in the market. Many people believe that the cash flows of a defaultable financial contract can be priced independently and then be summed up to give the final risky price of the contract. We emphasize here that this conclusion is only true of the financial

contracts whose payoffs are always positive. In the cases where the promised payoffs could be positive or negative, the valuation requires not only a backward recursive induction procedure, but also a strategic selection of different discount factors according to the market value in time. This coupled valuation process allows us to capture correlation between counterparties and market factors.

The bilateral CVA of the multiple-payment contract can be expressed as

$$CVA(t) = V^F(t) - V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ E[D(t, T_i) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t] - E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} K(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t \right] \right\} \quad (18)$$

3. Numerical Results

For risk-neutral simulation, we use a Hull-White model for interest rate and a CIR (Cox-Ingersoll-Ross) model for hazard rate scenario generations a modified GBM (Geometric Brownian Motion) model for equity and collateral evolution. The results are presented in the following tables. Table 2 illustrates that if party *A* has an infinite collateral threshold $H_A = \infty$ i.e., no collateral requirement on *A*, the CVA value increases while the threshold H_B increases. Table 3 shows that if party *B* has an infinite collateral threshold $H_B = \infty$, the CVA value actually decreases while the threshold H_A increases. This reflects the bilateral impact of the collaterals on the CVA. The impact is mixed in Table 4 when both parties have finite collateral thresholds.

Table 2. The impact of collateral threshold H_B on the CVA

This table shows that given an infinite H_A , the CVA increases while H_B increases, where H_B denotes the collateral threshold of party *B* and H_A denotes the collateral threshold of party *A*.

Collateral Threshold H_B	10.1 Mil	15.1 Mil	20.1 Mil	Infinite (∞)
CVA	19,550.91	20,528.65	21,368.44	22,059.30

Table 3. The impact of collateral threshold H_A on the CVA

This table shows that given an infinite H_B , the CVA decreases while H_A increases, where H_B denotes the collateral threshold of party B and H_A denotes the collateral threshold of party A .

Collateral Threshold H_A	10.1 Mil	15.1 Mil	20.1 Mil	Infinite (∞)
CVA	28,283.64	25,608.92	23,979.11	22,059.30

Table 4. The impact of the both collateral thresholds on the CVA

The CVA may increase or decrease while both collateral thresholds change, where H_B denotes the collateral threshold of party B and H_A denotes the collateral threshold of party A . This reflects the fact that the collaterals have bilateral impacts on the CVA.

Collateral Threshold H_B	10.1 Mil	15.1 Mil	20.1 Mil	Infinite (∞)
Collateral Threshold H_A	10.1 Mil	15.1 Mil	20.1 Mil	Infinite (∞)
CVA	25,752.98	22,448.45	23,288.24	22,059.30

Some financial markets are closely interlinked, while others are not. For example, CDS price movements have a feedback effect on the equity market, as a trading strategy commonly employed by banks and other market participants consists of selling a CDS on a reference entity and hedging the resulting credit exposure by shorting the stock. On the other hand, Moody's Investor's Service (2000) presents statistics that suggest that the correlations between interest rates and CDS spreads are very small.

We use an equity swap as an example. Assume the correlation between the underlying equity price and the credit quality (hazard rate) of party B is ρ . The impact of the correlation on the CVA is show in Table 5. The results say that the CVA increases when the absolute value of the negative correlation increases.

Table 5. The impact of wrong way risk on the CVA

This table shows that the CVA increases while the negative correlation ρ increases in the absolute value. We use an equity swap as an example and assume that there is a negative correlation between the equity price and the credit quality of party B .

Correlation ρ	0	-50%	-100%
CVA	165.15	205.95	236.99

4. Conclusion

An intuitive explanation is that two counterparties implicitly sell each other an option to default when entering into an OTC derivative transaction. If we assume that a default may occur at any time, the default options are American style options. If we assume that a default may only happen on the payment dates, the default options are Bermudan style options. Both Bermudan and American options require backward induction valuations.

Based on our theory, we propose a novel cash-flow-based framework (see appendix) for calculating bilateral CVA at the counterparty portfolio level. This framework can easily incorporate various credit mitigation techniques, such as netting agreements and margin agreements, and can capture wrong/right way risk. Numerical results show that these credit mitigation techniques and wrong/right way risk have significant impacts on CVA.

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